

WORKPLACE HAPPINESS AND EMPLOYEE COMMITMENT: INSIGHTS FROM NON-ACADEMIC STAFF AT DELTA STATE UNIVERSITY, NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study investigated the relationship between workplace happiness and organizational commitment (OC) of non-academic staff currently working at Delta State University Abraka, Nigeria. The study was guided by the following specific objectives: determine the relationship between compensation and OC, ascertain the relationship between workplace environment and OC and evaluate the relationship between work-life balance and OC. The survey research design was employed in this investigation. The study's population comprised of all non-academic staff of Delta State University Abraka, Nigeria. 156 employees were selected using a convenient sampling technique. A structured questionnaire was employed as a tool to collect data from the respondents. The data analysis techniques employed in this study were descriptive statistics, correlation coefficient and multiple regression analysis. The findings of the study established that compensation and work-life balance as indicators of workplace happiness have a positive and significant effect on OC. On the other hand, workplace environment has a positive and insignificant effect on OC. The study concluded that the indicators of work place happiness adopted in this study are a key stimulator of OC. Based on the result of this study, it was recommended that management should offer a competitive financial and non-financial rewards to boost employees morale, cultivate a positive and inclusive work environment where the employees feels valued and encourage flexible work arrangement to promote work-life balance.

Keywords: workplace happiness, compensation, workplace environment, work-life balance and organizational commitment

INTRODUCTION

The most valuable resource that determines the success or failure of an organization is its employees. Without a committed workforce, an organization cannot operate effectively and accomplish its stated goals and objectives. According to Walczak (2023), work psychology and management research is steadily demonstrating that employee commitment, engagement, productivity, and loyalty to the organization are all closely linked to workplace happiness. Employee retention is also influenced by happiness (Charles-Leija, Castro, Toledo, & BallesterosValdés, 2023). According to reports, one of the many issues Nigerian organizations face is a lack of organizational commitment (OC) (Oyo-Ita, 2018). OC is associated with higher work happiness and lower burnout (Dunaetz, Smyly, Fairley & Heykoop,

2020; Oyelakin, Shodeinde and Arandong (2021). Thus, when an employee's value is similar to that of the organization, an employee enjoys work happiness. As argued by Wziątek-Staśko and Gracjasz (2024) workplace happiness (WH) can influence satisfaction derived from work, development in a chosen career, style of leadership, job condition, and most especially value congruence or person organization fit. As stated by Bissett (2014), value can be congruent if personal and organizational values are consistent and agree, as well as if employees flex their principles to satisfy organizational expectations. When an organization's beliefs align with those of its members, the organization will benefit. Bao, Dolan and Tzafirir, (2012), argued that positive outcomes might include job satisfaction, reduce employee turnover, employee commitment, and increase in productivity. Employees and organizations that share values can build a dedicated workforce that can grow with the dynamic and competitive nature of a global business (Auster & Freeman, 2018). Employees who are completely happy with their position will carry out their duties properly and efficiently, demonstrating their commitment to the position and, by extension, to the organization in general (Agustienna&Drahen, 2020). This will provide the organization the opportunity to survive and remain highly competitive in the global business world (Radosavljević, Vesna&Dragić 2017). Employees may exhibit good/bad or positive/negative attitudes depending on so many factors found in the workplace (Ndubuisi-Okolo, Emmanuel &Anigbogu, 2017), and sometimes outside the workplace. The degree of commitment to the organization's aims and objectives may be impacted by this mindset. Workplace influences include factors like the work surroundings, managerial approach, and compensation, while factors outside of the workplace include factors like family history and financial circumstances. Analyzing employee satisfaction is crucial, and human resource professionals are required to do so. Keeping employees happy will enable them to perform their task efficiently, thus the happiness or well-being of an employee both physically and mentally is very important to the success of an organization (Bataineh, 2019), which can be achieved through employee commitment to organizational goals and objectives. Ferssizidis, Adams, Kashdan, Plummer, Mishra, &Ciarrochi, 2010) posited that employees who succeeds in growing their careers over time were as a result of happiness derived from work. Employee happiness has a direct effect on OC since it increases emotions, time, and energy dedicated to a task, a group of people, and an individual (Mateu, 2015). Several studies have been conducted on WH and OC. However relatively few studies have taken place in Nigeria. These altogether invoked the need for more scientific knowledge to ascertain if perhaps there is significant effect of WH (proxied by compensation, workplace environment, and work-life balance) on OC among non-academic staff of Delta State University, Abraka.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Workplace Happiness

The level of joy and fulfillment that people encounter in their professional lives is referred to as WH. According to Mateu (2015), happiness is a subjective concept that cannot be accurately evaluated and is contingent upon how an individual expresses it to others based on their perception, expectations, and the conditions of their particular setting. According to Wesarat, Sharif, and Majid (2015), an employee's

level of satisfaction with his personal and professional lives in general is a measure of his WH. As defined by Susniene and Jurkauskas (2019), happiness is a subjective assessment that is determined by a person's subjective perception of happiness and their personal quality of life. In this study, feelings of joy, contentment, fulfillment, and satisfaction are all considered to be essential elements of workplace happiness. There are 3 elements WH (1) Happy People: means employees are happy to work which will lead them to being a key personnel of the organization.(2) Happy Home: means the workplace which makes the employees feel that the workplace is the second home. It is the organization that has the creative coexistence and mutual development. (3) Happy Teamwork: means there is the cooperation among the employees (Wasanthanarat & Wuttiwatchaikaew, 2017). Employee engagement, autonomy and choicemaking, financial stability, room for innovative thinking and creativity, openness and empathy, obstacles and varied tasks, and work-life balance are all components that make people happy at work (Chowdhury, 2021). To enhance workplace happiness, organizations must pay attention to employee needs and promote a culture of inclusivity, recognition, meaningful engagement, positive colleague connections, and flexibility (Field & Buitendach, 2011). Programs for professional development, wellness resources, and well-defined career growth opportunities can substantially enhance morale. There are several indicators of WH. However, this study used compensation, workplace environment and work life-balance as indicators/measures of WH.

Compensation

Compensation is what workers get paid for their contributions to the organization. Compensation denotes the aggregate rewards and advantages an organization offers its employees in return for their labour and contributions. It encompasses direct financial remuneration, including salaries, commissions, wages, bonuses, and indirect benefits such as retirement plans, health insurance, and paid leave. Compensation is a crucial element of the employment (work) relationship, acting as a primary motivator for attracting, maintaining, and rewarding talent within an organization (Astuti, Pangaribuan & Noer, 2024). As cited by Rianaa and Wirasedanaa (2016), compensation can be used to: a) recruit and retain talented individuals; b) gain a competitive edge; c) encourage employees to achieve high-performance outcomes; d) pay employees in accordance with legal requirements; f) assist businesses in achieving their strategic objectives; and g) establish a strong organizational framework and its operation. According to Naidu and Satyanarayana (2018), compensation is the amount of money that an organization gives its workers as a thank you for their efforts and has a big impact on employee happiness. Benefits and remuneration are the most basic elements affecting employee performance, which in turn affects the organization's performance. Compensation or pay incentives are what can attract new hires, keep them on board, and help them succeed over time. Researchers often discover that the main factor affecting a prospective employee's willingness to take up a job offer is compensation. Silaban and Syah (2018) further stated that workers who are dissatisfied with their income are more inclined to leave and look for better-paying positions elsewhere. Employee satisfaction with compensation has a big impact on high turnover rates, which is a complicated issue for organizations. The use of compensation is one of the key methods that management can enhance

performance, commitment, motivation, and work achievement (Rianaa & Wirasedanaa, 2016). Additionally, according to Putra, Nurmayanti, and Suryatni (2022), compensation is one element that may influence OC. Employee loyalty and satisfaction will rise if compensation is given after the workload. Solihin, Aima, and Widyastuti (2019), contended that compensation is a type of expense that the business must bear in the hopes of receiving a return for employee success.

Workplace Environment (WPE)

WPE encompasses the psychological, social, physical and conditions under which employees execute their duties. It includes elements such as workplace architecture, resource availability, organizational culture, leadership styles, and interpersonal relationships among coworkers (Irawan & Ie, 2021). A good workplace atmosphere is crucial for enhancing productivity, creativity, and job satisfaction, whereas a detrimental environment may result in stress, unhappiness, and diminished performance (Al Hadi & Indrawan, 2024; Baharuddin, Ramly, Alam, & Kalla, 2020). The environment serves as a foundation that enables employees to perform at their highest potential. An effectively designed WPE emphasizes both physical and mental health of the employees. Easily operated furniture, sufficient lighting, and a tidy, organized office enhance comfort and efficiency. Okeoghene and Aina (2016) opined that a psychologically supportive environment, in which employees feel appreciated, respected, and acknowledged, improves morale and motivation. Transparent communication, collaborative opportunities, and acknowledgement of accomplishments are essential for fostering an engaging and inclusive atmosphere. Irawan and Ie (2021) further stated that employees are more inclined to perform better when they experience emotional and physical safety in their work environment. The advantages of a constructive workplace atmosphere are significant for both employees and organizations. Happy and committed employees demonstrate increased productivity, enhanced creativity, and a greater propensity to remain with the organization, hence minimizing turnover expenses (Al Hadi & Indrawan, 2024). This results in enhanced performance, fortified team dynamics, and a competitive edge in recruiting premier talent for the organization. Consequently, cultivating a healthy and inclusive working environment must be a strategic focus, since it directly influences employee well-being and organizational performance.

Work Life-Balance (WLB)

The proportion of time you spend working as opposed to the proportion of time you spend with your family and engaging in activities you enjoy is referred to as work-life balance. Worklife balance, according to Parkes and Langford (2008), is the capacity of workers to fulfill their obligations to their families, their jobs, and other extracurricular endeavors. Döckel (2003) opined that organizations must give workers access to child care facilities, videoconferencing options, assistance programs, and employee support initiatives to ensure a favorable work-life balance. Employees' emotional connection to their organizations is positively impacted by WLB regulations/policies, which they view as organizational care (Döckel, 2003). Work-life balance, in the words of Döckel (2003), is striking a balance between one's personal and professional lives while minimizing conflict between these many responsibilities so that one can complete both tasks. Working practices that acknowledge and aim to

support the needs of staff in achieving a balance between their personal and working life is essential for achieving organizational goals. Job satisfaction, interpersonal relationships, growth, advancement, and working circumstances all affect the quality of WLB (Subrahmanian & Anjani, 2010). The direct as well as indirect impacts of practices on the outcomes of various stakeholders in hospitals were investigated by Vloeberghs (2020). The findings unveil that hospitals, their staff, and the patients they treat benefit from increased usage of WLB approaches. In the opinion of Muse, Harris, Giles, and Field (2008), offering a WLB that employees appreciate is a component of a constructive relationship in which both the employer and the employee gain.

Organizational commitment (OC)

OC refers to the degree of recognition, acceptance and trust of employees towards the values and goals of the organization as well as the positive emotional experience they bring to themselves (Aruoren & Tarurhor, 2023; Aruoren & Ganni, 2023). Ismail and Sukkar (2020) define OC as a reaction of emotion which can range from very low to extremely high and is measured by people's behaviors, values, and attitudes. OC, according to Robbins and Judge (2017), is the extent to which a worker relates with a specific organization and its objectives and wishes to stay as an employee of the organization. Thus, because of their sense of loyalty or organizational attachment, committed employees are less inclined to leave their position, even if they have another offer (Aruoren & Oboreh, 2020). OC is an important outcome of employee happiness and job satisfaction (Aruoren & Oisamoje, 2023).

Conceptual Framework

Source: Researcher’s Conceptualization (2024)

Compensation and OC

Compensation is a crucial determinant of an employee's loyalty and commitment to their organization (Astuti, et al., 2024). Equitable and competitive remuneration frameworks signify that an organization appreciates its employees' contributions, hence cultivating trust and a sense of belonging. When employees view their compensation as fair and commensurate with their talents, effort, and market

benchmarks, they experience satisfaction and are more likely to maintain their commitment to the organization while being less motivated to pursue alternative options (Putra, et al., 2022). Compensation influences the psychological contract between employees and employers, which encompasses the implicit agreement over mutual expectations. In addition to financial remuneration, pay packages that encompass benefits such as bonuses, retirement plans, and health insurance enhance an employee's belief that their welfare is a priority for the organization (Rianaa & Wirasedanaa, 2016; Rizal, Idrus, Djumahir & Minta, 2014). Performancebased awards and career progression possibilities enhance OC by acknowledging and incentivizing employee efforts; thereby inspiring employees to remain engaged and committed to their firm. Employees who perceive inadequate compensation or lack of appreciation may experience dissatisfaction, disengagement, and potentially exit the organization, resulting in elevated turnover rates and diminished productivity (Putra, et al., 2022). To sustain robust OC, organizations must consistently evaluate their remuneration schemes to guarantee they are competitive, equitable, and aligned with employee expectations, thereby fostering a motivated and loyal workforce. Rizal, Idrus, Djumahir, and Minta (2014) investigated the relationship between compensation, motivation, and OC. The study population consisted of 1,394 employees that work at the Local Apparatus Work Unit (LAWU) at Local Revenue Management in Kendari. The study examined 126 employees using a random sampling method, and the data analysis method used was SEM (Structural Equation Model). The study's findings unveil that compensation has a significant impact on OC and motivation, though not on employee performance; OC and motivation have a significant impact on employee performance, and OC has a significant impact on employee performance. The effects of compensation on employee performance, OC on employee performance, compensation on OC, and the moderating role of a labor union on compensation and employee performance were all examined by Rianaa and Wirasedanaa (2016). Simple randomly sampling was utilized in this study to select 97 employees from a Bali-based cellular carrier company. A questionnaire was used to gather the data and partial least squares and descriptive analysis were used for analysis. The findings indicate that compensation has a positive and significant impact on OC and performance, while labor unions have a negative and significant moderating effect on both compensation and employee performance. OC also has a positive nonsignificant impact on performance. Putra, Nurmayanti, and Suryatni (2022) investigated the moderating function of employee job satisfaction at Air Minum Giri Menang Ltd on the impact of career development and compensation on OC. There were 96 employees in the sample. A questionnaire was used for data collection in the study while data analysis was done using Structural Equation Model Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS). The findings demonstrated that career development and compensation have a favorable and significant impact on OC and job satisfaction. Additionally, through the job satisfaction of Air MinumGiriMenang Ltd. employees, compensation and career development have a good and significant impact on OC. Astuti, Pangaribuan, and Noer (2024) studied how OC was impacted by compensation, career advancement, and job satisfaction. Participants in the study included 148 Class III UPBU office workers from the Merauke district of Indonesia. A 5-point Likert scale questionnaire was utilized to obtain data, and path analysis was used for analysis. The

findings demonstrated that while compensation has no direct effect on OC, it does have positive effects on job satisfaction. Additionally, it was discovered that career development improved OC and job satisfaction. Lastly, job satisfaction moderated the association between OC and compensation/career growth and was positively correlated with OC. Thus, we propose that:

H01: There is no significant link between compensation and OC.

Workplace Environment and OC

A favorable WPE cultivates job happiness, motivation, and a sense of belonging, hence improving employees' commitment to their positions and the organization overall (NwabuezeKelvin & Aruoren, 2023; Irawan & Ie, 2021). Elements including transparent communication, encouraging leadership, and avenues for professional development foster an atmosphere in which employees feel appreciated and involved. Employees who regard their workplace as inclusive, secure, and conducive to productivity may be more inclined to demonstrate elevated levels of OC (Aruoren & Ugbeghene, 2023; Baharuddin, Ramly, Alam & Kalla, 2020). A detrimental workplace atmosphere can undermine OC. Toxic work cultures typified by bad management, lack of appreciation, and extreme stress often lead to disengagement, unhappiness and high turnover rates (Okeoghene & Aina, 2016). Employees in such environments may feel unappreciated, lonely, or unfulfilled, decreasing their emotional interest in the organization. This disengagement and discontent not only lowers individual performance but also impairs team interactions and overall organizational success. In Ghana's banking industry, Ahakwa, Yang, Tackie, and Atingabili (2021) investigated the relationship between job satisfaction, WPE, and employee engagement on OC and employee performance while taking moderated-mediated interaction into consideration. Using basic random probability sampling, data was gathered from 720 employees of selected financial banks in Ghana's Greater Accra Region. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)-based partial least squares (PLS) and weighted partial least squares (WPLS) were used in the analysis. According to the study's findings, there is a positive and significant relationship between (1) employee engagement and OC, (2) employee engagement and performance, (3) WPE and OC, (4) WPE and performance, (5) OC and performance, (6) job satisfaction and performance, (7) the moderating role of job satisfaction, and (8) the mediation role of OC. The aim of Mambrasar, Lengkong, and Taroreh (2021) study was to examine how OC is impacted by WPE, punishments, rewards, and discipline. A survey approach was employed in the study. The study's population of 43 respondents included every employee of the Tambrauw Financial Management Agency Office with a sample of 37 employees. Based on the analyzed data via multiple linear regression, OC is impacted simultaneously by the WPE, rewards, punishments, and discipline. Work discipline has a positive and significant impact on OC, while the WPE, rewards, and punishments have a positive and insignificant effect on OC. Al Hadi and Indrawan (2024) investigate how work stress in Indonesia mediates the relationship between organizational culture, WPE and OC. The research methodology used in the study was quantitative. Seventy Bank Indonesia, North Sumatra employees made up the study's population, and the study sample was the same as the entire population. For data analysis, the study made use of smartPLS SEM (Partial Least Square – Structural Equation Modeling) software. Findings indicated that OC is

positively and insignificantly impacted by organizational culture. Job stress is significantly and negatively impacted by organizational culture. OC is positively and insignificantly impacted by the WPE. Stress at work is significantly and negatively impacted by the WPE. OC is negatively and significantly impacted by job stress. Through work stress, the WPE has a positive and insignificant impact on OC. Thus, we propose that:

H02: There is no significant link between workplace environment and OC.

Work-life balance and OC

WLB plays a key part in establishing OC, which is an employee's emotional attachment and devotion to their organization. Employees that strike a healthy balance between their working and personal lives are often more satisfied, joyful, motivated, and engaged (Hutagalung, Soelton & Octaviani, 2020). This balance helps minimize stress, increases general well-being, and fosters a good view of the organization. When organizations incorporate flexible work arrangements, fair workloads, and supportive policies, employees frequently feel appreciated and are more likely to demonstrate higher levels of dedication to the organization (Hutagalung, et al., 2020). Additionally, poor WLB can have a severe effect on OC. Employees who struggle to manage work obligations alongside personal duties may develop burnout, discontent, and animosity toward their employer (Swamy, Aruna & Pradeep, 2023). This imbalance can lead to disengagement, poor productivity, and higher turnover rates. Organizations that fail to address WLB risk losing important talent and tarnishing their reputation as a desirable environment. Employees are less likely to stay devoted with an employer that does not promote their holistic well-being. Addressing the importance of work-life balance, organizations may create stronger relationships with their employees and foster a workplace environment that fosters long-term commitment and organizational progress. Using OC as an intervening variable, Hutagalung, Soelton, and Octaviani (2020) examined the effects of emotional intelligence and WLB on turnover intention. A descriptive research approach was employed in this study. With a sample of 60 respondents, the study's population consisted of workers at a company that distributes computer spare parts. Structural Equation Model (SEM) with Smart-PLS analysis tool was used for data analysis. The findings demonstrate that OC was positively and significantly impacted by work-life balance. OC was positively and significantly impacted by emotional intelligence. WLB significantly and negatively impacted the intention to leave. In the end, OC significantly and negatively affects turnover intention, whereas emotional intelligence significantly and positively influences it. Swamy, Aruna, and Pradeep (2023) examined how WLB affects the commitment of workers in IT firms. Convenience sampling served as the foundation for the study. In order to gather data for the study, a standardized questionnaire were given to 100 respondents from selected IT organizations in Bangalore. ANOVA was utilized to test the hypothesis and determine the association between the sample respondents' commitment and WLB after the obtained data was evaluated using descriptive statistics. The study's findings demonstrated that WLB has a substantial and significant impact on employee commitment. Wziątek-Staśko and Gracjasz (2024) investigated the connection between OC and happiness. The qualitative approach was used as a framework for the study. A sample of 220 Polish employees participated in the November 2023 CAWI survey, which was

used to gather opinions on the link between the stated components. According to research findings, happiness is positively correlated with OC. Field and Buitendach (2011) examined the relationship between work engagement, happiness, and OC. A cross-sectional survey design was employed by the researchers. They employed a sample of 123 support staff members from a South African higher education establishment. According to the findings, the researchers discovered a strong positive correlation between affective OC and both work engagement and happiness. They discovered a strong correlation between happiness and work engagement. Lastly, the findings demonstrated the predictive relevance of work engagement and happiness on affective OC. Therefore, we propose that:

Ho3: There is no significant link between work-life balance and OC.

Theoretical Framework

This study is hinged on the Social Exchange Theory (SET). Social Exchange Theory offers a significant paradigm for comprehending the correlation between workplace happiness and OC. SET posits that relationships are established through reciprocal transactions, wherein individuals strive to equilibrate the advantages they obtain with the contributions they render. In a professional environment (workplace context), when employees perceive equity, support, and acknowledgement from their organization, they experience a need to reciprocate with heightened commitment (Wziątek-Staśko & Gracjasz, 2024). Workplace happiness, influenced by elements such as pleasant connections, supportive leadership, and possibilities for advancement, enhances employees' emotional investment in their organization, hence reinforcing their commitment (Field & Buitendach, 2011). Happy employees perceive their organization as one that appreciates their contributions and fulfils their demands, thereby establishing a positive feedback cycle. This emotional bond compels people to exceed fundamental job expectations and dedicate greater effort to their responsibilities. Conversely, when employees experience dissatisfaction due to inadequate treatment, insufficient recognition, or an unsupportive atmosphere, their sense of reciprocity diminishes, thereby undermining their commitment. SET elucidates that the perceived disparity in the transaction may result in disengagement or potential turnover. The reciprocal nature of SET highlights that workplace happiness and OC are interrelated and mutually reinforcing. Organizations that emphasize employee well-being and foster a pleasant work culture benefit from a dedicated and loyal team. Happy employees are more inclined to synchronize their aspirations with organizational goals, whereas organizations that acknowledge and reward this allegiance promote enduring engagement and productivity.

METHODOLOGY

The survey research design was employed in this investigation. This research design was adopted to enable the researcher obtain primary data from the study respondents. All the nonacademic staff currently working at Delta State University Abraka, Nigeria made up the study's total population. A structured questionnaire was employed as a tool to collect data from the respondents, and 156 employees were selected using a convenient sampling technique. Data analysis employed included correlation coefficient, multiple regression analysis, and descriptive statistics. Additionally, Microsoft Excel software was used to create tables and input data.

Measurement

The two constructs under investigation (WH and OC) were measured by scales adopted from previous studies. WH (compensation, workplace environment and work-life balance) were measured by a modified version of workplace happiness indicator survey developed by Dockel (2003), Hanaysha (2016) and Ahakwa et al. (2021). Compensation was assessed by 5 items, workplace environment was assessed using 4 items and WLB was also measured with 4 items. OC was also measured with 5 items by a modified version of OC questionnaire (OCQ) developed by Mowday, Steer and Porter (1979). All the variables were measured on a 4 point Likert scale ranging from (4) strongly agreed to (1) strongly disagreed.

Model Specification

$$OC = f(\text{COMP}, \text{WPE}, \text{WLB})$$

$$OC = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1\text{COMP} + \alpha_2\text{WPE} + \alpha_3\text{WLB} + \varepsilon_1$$

Where, OC = Organizational commitment; COMP = Compensation; WPE= Workplace Environment; WLB = Work-life balance; α_0 = Constant term; $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3,$ = Regression coefficients ε_1 = Error term

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The demographic data of the respondents with respect to sex, age, marital status, educational qualification were presented in Table 1. The result on respondents sex indicates that 68(45%) of the respondents were male, while 84(55%) of the respondents were female. Regarding the respondents age, the result indicates that 12(7.9%) of the respondents were within the age bracket of 20-30years, 34(22.4%) were within the age bracket of 31 – 40years, 51(33.6%) were within the age bracket of 41 – 50years and 55(36.1%) were within the age bracket 51 – 60years. With regards to marital status, 122(80.3%) of the respondents are married, 28(18.4%) are single while 2(1.3%) are divorced. Also, educational background of the respondents unveiled that 23(15.1%) are OND holders, 89(58.6%) are HND and BSc holders while 40(26.3%) are MBA and M.Sc holders.

Table 1. Demographic Variable of the Respondents

Variables	Parameters	Frequency	Percentage
Respondent Sex	Male	68	45%
	Female	84	55%
	Total	152	100%
Respondents Age	20 – 30	12	7.9%
	31 – 40	34	22.4%
	41 – 50	51	33.6%
	51 – 60	55	36.1%
	Total	152	100%
Marital status	Married	122	80.3%
	Single	28	18.4%

	Divorced	2	1.3%
	Total	152	100%
Educational Qualification	OND	23	15.1%
	HND/BSc	89	58.6%
	MBA/MSc	40	26.3%
	Total	152	100%

Source: Authors computation, 2024

The descriptive statistics of all the variables are presented in Table 2. The results unveiled that all the items on compensation (COMP 1 – COMP 5), workplace environment (WPE 1 – WPE 6), work-life balance (WLB 1 – WLB 4) and OC (OC 1 – OC 5) scored above the 2.0 cut-off point of mean when a 4 point Likert scale is used in a study. This suggests that the respondents see all of the items as accurate indicators of the variables. The absence of variance in the responses obtained from the study respondents is shown by the standard deviation value for each item (standard deviation of all the items are less than 1).

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Items	Mean	Standard Deviation
COMP 1	3.81	0.50
COMP 2	3.85	0.49
COMP 3	3.68	0.50
COMP 4	3.47	0.61
COMP 5	3.67	0.47
WPE 1	3.39	0.54
WPE 2	3.09	0.88
WPE 3	3.39	0.53
WPE 4	3.36	0.53
WPE 5	3.65	0.48
WPE 6	3.57	0.50
WLB 1	3.22	0.69
WLB 2	3.38	0.65
WLB 3	3.50	0.59
WLB 4	3.67	0.60
OC 1	3.50	0.68
OC 2	3.43	0.54
OC 3	3.45	0.64
OC 4	3.73	0.46
OC 5	3.58	0.51

Source: Authors computation, 2024

The Cronbach alpha test was employed to test the reliability of the instrument. The results demonstrated that the instrument measured the variables that it was intended to measure, as the mean score was greater than 0.5 benchmark. Table 3 presents the Cronbach alpha results. **Table 3:**

Reliability Test

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
Compensation	0.848	5
Workplace Environment	0.906	6
Work-life balance	0.872	4
Organizational commitment	0.865	5
Mean Score	0.872	

Source: Authors computation, 2024

The results of the independent variables' variance inflator factor (VIF) are shown in Table 4. A test that is used to ascertain whether multicollinearity exists among the independent variables used in a study is the variance inflator factor. Since the mean value of all the independent variable were not greater than the benchmark ($1.84 < 10$), it suggests that there is no multicollinearity among the independent variables employed in this investigation. The VIF result is displayed in Table 4.

Table 4.: Variance inflator factor

Independent Variable	VIF	I/VIF
Compensation	2.31	0.433
Workplace Environment	1.99	0.501
Work-life balance	1.23	0.815
Mean VIF	1.84	

Source: Authors computation, 2024

Table 5 displays the correlation matrix between OC and the indicators of WH (compensation, WLB, and workplace environment). A correlation coefficient of 0.568 was found for the link between COMP and OC. Additionally, a correlation coefficient of 0.339 regarding the association between OC and WPE was found. Furthermore, a correlation coefficient of 0.874 was found for the link between WLB and OC. This suggests that there is a positive correlation between OC and all indicators of WH.

Table 5: Correlation matrix

	COMP	WPE	WLB	OC
COMP Pearson Correlation	1			
Sig. (2-tailed)				
N	152			

WPE	Pearson Correlation	0.689** 0.000		1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
	N	152	152		
WLB	Pearson Correlation	0.408** 0.000	0.168* 0.022	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
	N	152	152	201	
OC	Pearson Correlation	0.568** 0.000	0.339** 0.000	0.874** 0.000	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)				
	N	152	152	152	152

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)
Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Authors computation, 2024

Test of Hypotheses

Multiple regression analysis used in testing the hypotheses. Based on the result shown in Table 6, a regression parameter of 0.292, and a t-value of 4.23 with p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$ was obtained between COMP and OC. This is clear indications that COMP as an indicator of WH has a positive and significant effect on the OC. Therefore, the stated null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis accepted. Also, a regression parameter of 0.040, and a t-value of 0.74 with pvalue of $0.458 > 0.05$ was obtained between WPE and OC. The coefficient parameter and p-value obtained between WPE and OC means that WPE has a positive but insignificant effect on OC. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. Furthermore, a regression parameter of 0.986 and a t-value of 19.91 with a p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$ was also found between WLB and OC indicating that WLB) has a positive and significant effect on OC. Based on this premises, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis accepted. Overall, the regression model's R-squared value of 0.817 indicates that 81.7% of the variation in OC can be explained by the workplace happiness indicators (COMP, WPE, and WLB). Furthermore, goodness of fit is indicated by the adjusted R-squared value of 0.814. Because the independent variables were able to predict the dependent variable, this indicates that the model as a whole is significant based on the adjusted R-squared value of 0.814.

Table 6: Multiple Regression Analysis

Dependent Variable: Organizational commitment
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Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error.	t-statistics	p-value
Compensation (COMP)	0.292	0.07	4.23	0.000
Workplace Environment (WPE)	0.040	0.05	0.74	0.458
Work-life balance (WLB)	0.986	0.05	19.91	0.000
Constant	-2.089	0.95	-2.204	0.029
Prob> F (220.956)				0.000
R-squared				0.817
Adj R-squared				0.814

Source: Authors computation, 2024

Discussion of Findings

This study focused the linkage between workplace happiness (compensation, WPE, WLB) and OC of non-academic staff of Delta State University Abraka, Nigeria. The result unveiled that compensation has a positively and significantly effect on OC. This suggests that when employees view their remuneration as equitable, sufficient, and commensurate with their contributions, their allegiance to the organization intensifies. Compensation, encompassing salary, bonuses, perks, and non-monetary rewards, acts as a crucial motivator and a concrete recognition of employees' contributions. Employees who perceive their compensation as competitive and equitable are more inclined to cultivate a deeper emotional connection to the organization. This result is consistent with the results of Rizal et al. (2014), Rianaa and Wirasedanaa (2016), Putra et al. (2022), Astuti et al. (2024) who found that compensation significantly and positively fosters employee’s level of OC. Furthermore, WPE has a positive and insignificant effect on OC indicating a minor upward movement that suggests an improved WPE may enhance employee commitment, but the impact lacks sufficient statistical significance to be considered meaningful. The insignificance of this relationship may arise from various factors. This research suggests that, although the WPE is influential, other elements may be more pivotal in fostering OC. Employees may regard the work environment as adequate, yet insufficiently remarkable to affect their emotional commitment or sense of duty. This finding concur with the results of Mambrasar et al. (2021), Al Hadi and Indrawan (2024) who found that WPE has a positive and insignificant effect on employees' level of OC. Furthermore, it was discovered that WLB has a positive and significant effect on OC. Employees who successfully manage their personal and professional life tend to be happier, more content, more driven, and more engaged. This equilibrium reduces stress, improves overall health, and cultivates a positive perception of the organization. Employees usually feel valued and are more inclined to unveil greater levels of OC when organizations implement flexible work schedules, equitable workloads, and encouraging rules. This finding agrees with the results of Hutagalung et al. (2020), Swamy et al. (2023) who found that WLB is positively and significantly related to OC.

Conclusively, WH is positively and significantly related to OC of non-academic staff of Delta State University Abraka, Nigeria. This is also in line with previous studies like Field and Buitendach (2011), Oyelakin et al. (2021), Wziątek-Staśko and Gracjasz (2024) who found that WH is positively and significantly related to OC.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study explored the relationship between WH (proxied by compensation, WPE, and WLB) and OC of non-academic staff of Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria. The findings of the study indicated that compensation and WLB as indicators of WH have a positive and significant effect on OC while WPE has a positive and insignificant effect on OC. In conclusion, the indicators of WH are a key stimulator of OC. Based on the result of this study, it is recommended that management should offer a competitive financial and non-financial rewards to boost employees morale, cultivate a positive and inclusive WPE where the employees feels valued and encourage flexible work arrangement to promote WLB.

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